

Studies on Some Physical Properties of Sesame Oil in Mixed Solvents

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The mutual solubility of sesame oil in ethanol by another solvent, *n*-hexane, cyclohexane or isopropanol was increased by increasing the temperature of the solution. Physical properties—density, viscosity, surface tension and refractive index of the solubilized solution of sesame oil in the mixed solvents have been studied at the temperature at which solution becomes clear.

THE mutual solubility of two normally immiscible liquids may increase by the addition of a third substance which acts at the interface of two immiscible liquids. This phenomenon, known as solubilization, depends on the nature of the solvent, chain length, temperature and presence of various additives. A solubilized product is clear because the particle size of the emulsion is so small that light is not refracted by the particles.

Sugiyama *et al*¹ used the highly concentrated solution of color-formers in mineral or vegetable oils and solubilized them by the addition of organic peroxides. Lubowe² solubilized the mixture of lower alcohols (1-3C atoms) and mineral, vegetable and animal oils by the addition of proportions of fatty alcohols having 10-24C atoms. Kharin, *et al*³ studied density, refractive index, viscosity and surface tension of three component systems. Lazarev⁴, studied the surface tension of an ideal ternary solution. Butler, *et al*⁵ studied density, surface tension, viscosity, refractive index of ternary system Benzene-Cyclohexane Hexane.

Experimental

In the present work sesame oil has been employed to increase its solubility in ethanol using *n*-hexane, cyclohexane or isopropanol and studied the physical properties—density, viscosity, surface tension and refractive index of its solubilized solutions. The variation of these physical properties of solubilized solution of sesame oil in mixed solvents of ethanol with above mentioned solvents have been studied at the temperature at which solution becomes clear.

The general procedure adopted was to add, using a magnetic stirrer, appropriate amount of another solvent (*n*-hexane, cyclohexane or isopropanol) in the mixture of sesame oil in ethanol, but as another solvent is added in the mixture, turbidity appears which disappeared after increasing the

temperature of the solution. At this temperature sesame oil is said to be solubilized in ethanol. The amount of ethanol and above mentioned solvents in each set of observation was fixed and that of sesame oil was varied. Thermostat was used to increase the temperature of the solution till a transparent one phase system is obtained and then studied the above mentioned physical properties of the transparent solution at this temperature. Ethanol used was of 98% purity. In each set solution was prepared by weight ranging from 2 gm to 10 gm of oil and the weight of ethanol and the other solvent was fixed 50 gm each. The weight fraction of sesame oil is calculated, at a temperature at which solution becomes clear.

In each set viscosity of the solubilized solution was determined by Ostwald viscometer and was calculated by the usual method. Surface tension of the solution was determined by double capillary rise method of Richards, Speyer and Carvar⁶, with slight modification using the formula $\gamma_{\text{solution}} = KHd$, where γ_{solution} = surface tension of solution, H = difference in height, d = density of the solution and K = apparatus constant. Difference in height was measured by cathetometer. Refractive index of the solution was measured by Abbe's refractometer. Observations were taken at the temperature at which solution become clear. The characteristics of the sesame oil used were :

At 30° sp. gravity 0.9134 gm/c. c., viscosity 42.1932 c. p., surface tension 24.3245 dynes/cm, refractive index 1.4702.

In tables 1-3, the data of the weight fraction of sesame oil, density, viscosity, surface tension and refractive index of the solubilized solution of sesame oil in above mentioned mixed solvents have been shown.

Discussion

The variation of the viscosity, surface tension and refractive index of the solubilized solution of

TABLE 1—SESAME OIL-ETHANOL-*n*-HEXANE(Ethanol & *n*-hexane were taken 50 gm each at the temperature at which clear solution is obtained)

Weight fraction of sesame oil at the temperature at which clear solution is obtained	Temperature at which clear solution is obtained	Density of the solution in gm/c.c.	Viscosity of solution in c.p. η_{solution}	Surface tension of solution in dynes/cm γ_{solution}	Refractive index of the solution μ_{solution}
24×10^{-3}	25°	0.7451	0.8261	27.9985	1.3750
48×10^{-3}	30°	0.7468	0.8399	21.1866	1.3780
70×10^{-3}	35°	0.7484	0.8699	17.8534	1.3810
91×10^{-3}	40°	0.7574	0.8815	15.8767	1.3844
112×10^{-3}	45°	0.7595	0.8980	14.9684	1.3870

TABLE 2—SESAME OIL-ETHANOL-CYCLOHEXANE

(Ethanol & Cyclohexane were taken 50 gm each at the temperature at which solution becomes clear)

Weight fraction of sesame oil at the temperature at which clear solution is obtained	Temperature at which clear solution is obtained	Density of solution in gm/c.c.	Viscosity of solution in c.p. η_{solution}	Surface tension of solution in dynes/cm. γ_{solution}	Refractive index of the solution μ_{solution}
23×10^{-3}	30°	0.7894	0.9092	21.2568	1.3900
45×10^{-3}	35°	0.7969	0.9362	16.0996	1.3930
66×10^{-3}	40°	0.7998	0.9582	13.6806	1.3960
79×10^{-3}	45°	0.8675	0.9762	12.0208	1.3990
94×10^{-3}	50°	0.8994	0.9820	11.7245	1.4020

TABLE 3—SESAME OIL-ETHANOL-ISOPROPANOL

(Ethanol & Isopropanol were taken 50 gm each at the temperature at which clear solution is obtained)

Weight fraction of sesame oil at the temperature at which clear solution is obtained	Temperature at which clear solution is obtained	Density of solution in gm/c.c.	Viscosity of solution in c.p. η_{solution}	Surface tension of solution in dynes/cm γ_{solution}	Refractive index of the solution μ_{solution}
22×10^{-3}	38°	0.8024	1.3293	24.8296	1.3800
44×10^{-3}	45°	0.7962	1.2872	27.4895	1.3830
66×10^{-3}	50°	0.7892	1.2462	29.7824	1.3860
88×10^{-3}	55°	0.7817	1.2281	31.8432	1.3910
110×10^{-3}	60°	0.7751	1.2162	33.6243	1.3970

sesame oil in mixed solvents (Ethanol with *n*-Hexane, Cyclohexane and Isopropanol) with the weight fraction of sesame oil at the temperature at which clear solution is obtained—is shown in Fig 1. Curves A, B, C show the variation of viscosity with the weight fraction of oil and Curves A', B', C', the variation of surface tension with the weight fraction of oil when *n*-hexane, cyclohexane and isopropanol were used for increasing the solubility of sesame oil in ethanol respectively. These curves show that in the case of *n*-hexane and cyclohexane, viscosity of

the solution increases while surface tension decreases with the weight fraction of oil but in the case of isopropanol viscosity decreases and surface tension increases. It may likely be due to the fact that isopropanol is more polar than *n*-hexane and cyclohexane. Curves A'', B'', C'' show the variation of refractive index with the weight fraction of oil. These curves show that in each case refractive index of the solution increases with the weight fraction of oil which indicates that refractive index is independent on the polarity of another solvent, The

Fig. 1.

variation of the above mentioned physical properties with the temperature at which clear solution is obtained, is similar to the weight fraction effect.

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